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Predictors of study success for students of civil engineering at the beginning of their studies

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ABSTRACT

Engineering courses make high demands on students in subject and motivational skills. Problems with subject-specific requirements often lead to students terminating their engineering studies prematurely [1]. The presented research project investigates the question of which characteristics at the beginning of the studies predestine academic success. This relates to a perspective on characteristics that prevent unsuccessful students from achieving academic success.

There are study success models that contain in particular the grade of university entrance qualification (Abi) and personality traits as predictors (e.g. [2]). We assume that additional subject-specific predictors and regulatory strategies of individual resources determine academic success [3]. For this purpose, we have developed test

and questionnaire instruments and presented them to about 180 first-year students of civil engineering. The test instruments refer to the subject engineering mechanics (EM) and technical knowledge (FW), subject-specific modelling ability (MF) [4] and mathematical knowledge (MW) [5]. Success in studies is defined as written exam performance and subject-specific knowledge after the first semester.

In path models, we can demonstrate significant correlations between Abi, intelligence, subject-specific skills and mathematical knowledge on the one hand and the study success variables on the other ($N=177$; $\chi^2=3,387$; $CFI=1$; $RMSEA=0$). From a subject-specific perspective, particularly mathematical knowledge at the beginning of a course is therefore very important for the success of study. In the paper we will present the above models and analyses of the mathematical knowledge test at task level.

1 INTRODUCTION

In its attractiveness as a bridge to a profession, higher education has recently overtaken alternative paths such as vocational training. Surveys by the Federal Statistical Office show that since 2011 between 55 and 58% of graduates start university studies [6]. There are many ways to study at university. Through the objective of education policy to increase the permeability of the education system people with different educational background enter the universities. Those are challenged to deal with heterogeneous groups of study beginners.

However, first and foremost, the students themselves, with their respective educational biographies, have to pass the requirements of the university system. This is still oriented towards a high degree of independence and offers only limited support compared to school teaching and learning opportunities. The question arises whether, in particular, students with a lack of basic technical knowledge and ability succeed in complying with the requirements of higher education, especially at the beginning of their studies.

In this study, students of civil engineering were accompanied in the initial phase of their studies. This article describes the importance of mathematical knowledge at the start of the semester for the performance of the exam after the first semester, and whether students succeed in working through technical deficits within the first semester.

2 INITIAL SITUATION

The failure of studies appears mostly in the fact that exams are not passed or a study is even canceled. Especially in engineering courses, the number of students who finish their studies prematurely is high. According to Heublein et al. [1] the reasons for dropping out are often diverse and understood as an interaction of several reasons. These refer to the personal situation of the students, the study conditions, the professional orientation or the requirements in the study [1]. Heublein et al. [1] show that in particular the requirements of the study were mentioned most often or even as the decisive reason for the disenrollment.

Study requirements in a technical perspective are often used in empirical examinations, for example in the form of a written exam, as a dependent variable "study success" [5]. Several variables at study entry were identified as predictors. These are, for example, the grade of university entrance qualification, personality traits

(big five) or learning behaviour [eg. 2, 6, 7, 8]. As technical predictors of study success, the mathematical and subject-specific knowledge of the beginning of studies is shown in examinations [eg. 5]. The inclusion of technical knowledge and skills in study success models was only undertaken in recent studies, for example in the project “KoM@ING” [eg. 3, 9], in which mathematical as well as subject-specific competencies were assessed at the start of the study. In the investigations of this project first tendencies to correlations between mathematical previous knowledge and professional competences after the first semester occurred. It is clear from these findings that especially those students who have a certain performance potential, who already have specific knowledge and skills at the beginning of their studies, and who are likely to use this knowledge and skills profitably in their studies, will be successful.

The importance of especially mathematical knowledge and abilities at the beginning of studies is also made clear in surveys that were carried out among lecturers of the study entry phase in STEM programs (STEM: Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics). In the publications of the cosh group [10] and in the project “MaLeMINT” [11] concrete mathematical contents and examples are given.

If study requirements are interpreted as subject-specific study requirements, there is a tendency for those first-year-students to drop out, who do not have the specific technical knowledge and skills, also who are unable to work through these deficits within the first study phase. For the development of institutionally anchored and targeted support measures, it is crucial to know which technical knowledge and skills are available or not. Therefore, this article presents the test results from an empirical survey of the study success on the item level. In doing so, we investigate the following research questions (RQ):

RQ 1: Are there any correlations between the achieved item solution rates and the mathematical test contents in the test results?

RQ 2: Do students of civil engineering at the beginning of the study have comparable performance levels with regard to mathematical knowledge?

3 DATA BASE

In the study, which is part of the DFG researchgroup ALSTER (Academic learning and study success in the entry phase of science and technology study programs) [13] 208 students of civil engineering were accompanied by regular surveys in the first two semesters of their studies. For these students, information is available at the beginning of studies and at the end of the first semester. Information at the beginning of studies are, for example, the grade of university entrance qualification (Abi), the basic cognitive ability (KFT [12]), the mathematical (RF_T1) and subject-specific knowledge (FW_T1) or the subject-specific modeling ability (MF_T1) as well as the last achieved grade in mathematics (math) at school. This variable "math" has two levels. In the German Gymnasium, mathematics can be learned at a basic level and a performance level. This level difference is not taken into account in the variable. At the end of the first semester, the students were tested again for their professional achievements, for example with the Test for Mathematical Knowledge (RF_T2). The academic success variable is the average grade of the examinations in Engineering Mechanics (EM) and Advanced Mathematics (HM), which was achieved at the end of the first semester.

Statistical correlations of the recorded data were checked by means of a hierarchical regression. As a dependent variable (DV) serves the achieved average exam score in EM and HM (*Table 1*). In Model 1, the variable 'Abi' is used as an independent variable that can explain 24,37 % of the variance of DV. In model 2, the variable KFT is added, thus increasing the variance elucidation from DV to 28.42%. Model 3 also includes the variable math, which does not generate a significant charge to DV. The variance elucidation increases again, but the variable math does not provide any added value. In model 4, the variable math is no longer taken into account; the variable KFT also no longer shows a significant correlation and is removed from the model. The variables FW_T1, MF_T1 and RF_T1 are added. With this model, a variance of 46.26% can be clarified. In addition, the variables MF_T1 and RF_T1 show significant relationships to DV. Model 4 is therefore best suited to the data. Important variables for the explanation of DV are therefore RF_T1, MF_T1 and Abi. A detailed description of the modeling of this regression model will be presented at [4].

Table 1. Hierarchical regression, DV: average exam score in EM- and HM after semester 1

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
constant	0,033	0,025	0,017	0,057
Abi	0,492***	0,497***	0,581***	0,318***
KFT		0,155*	0,165*	
math			0,108	
FW_T1				-0,027
MF_T1				0,196*
RF_T1				0,448***
corr. R ²	24,37 %	28,42 %	30,87 %	46,26 %
df	175	170	158	161
p	1,775e-12	1,673e-13	2,813e-13	2,2e-16
p < 0,1'; 0,05*; 0,01**; 0,001***				

As a result, model 4 provides the comparatively largest explanation of variance with respect to the dependent variable and is thus to be preferred in this model comparison. If variables of the basic cognitive ability, the grade of university entrance qualification, the grade in mathematics and subject variables are included in the model, then the variables of the basic cognitive ability and the mathematics grade do not become significant and thus fall outside the model. Also, the subject-specific knowledge at the beginning of the study shows in model 4 no significant influence on the performance in the exams EM and HM. On the other hand, influences are reflected in the subject-specific modeling ability, the mathematical knowledge and the grade of university entrance qualification (Abi).

These three variables account for approximately 46.3% of the average exam grade in EM and HM after the first semester. This can also be explained in terms of content, because the content of the technical requirements of the EM and HM exams is focused on mathematical and subject-specific (in the case of EM contents of mechanics)

content. However, the great importance of the technical knowledge and abilities at the beginning of studies shows that the success of the exam is especially successful for those students who already have the necessary knowledge and skills at the beginning of their studies. They seem to succeed in the exam significantly better.

The following chapter introduces the test used to measure mathematical knowledge (RF_T1) and then examines the mathematical knowledge of the students from an item based perspective.

4 CALCULATION ABILITY AT STUDY BEGINNING

The test instrument for the acquisition of mathematical knowledge was published [5] and consists of 27 items in the content areas "calculation", "terms and equations", "vectors and matrices", "differentiate", "integrate" and "trigonometry". The tasks were presented to the students in a half-open answer format, the test instrument as a whole in a paper & pencil form. No further aids were available for the students. In the study of mathematical knowledge there are data from 196 of the 208 students of the cohort. These achieved a mean solution rate of $M = .54$ with a standard deviation of $SD = .24$. From an IRT-analysis of the test data results a very good EAP reliability of the test of $.87$. *Table 2* below shows the mathematical content areas of the instrument already mentioned, the respective number of items and the corresponding solution rates.

Table 2. Content areas of the test instrument for measuring mathematical knowledge

Content area	Number of items	solution rate
calculation	3	.83
vectors and matrices	7	.62
trigonometry	2	.57
differentiate	3	.45
terms and equitations	9	.43
integrate	3	.44

The contents represented in the test instrument are based on the already mentioned surveys of teachers regarding mathematics at the beginning of the study regarding the expected mathematical knowledge and abilities at this time [10, 11].

5 PERFORMANCE CLUSTERS

Students will be considered as successful after the first semester if they have shown high performance in the exams of the EM and HM and have received corresponding exam grades. These notes are used to build performance clusters (PC) in this chapter, and then to compare these clusters with various other features, such as mathematical knowledge.

5.1 CONSTITUTE THE CLUSTER

The group of students was divided into four performance clusters in this sub-study. The final examination grades in EM and HM were subdivided into four ranges, as shown in *Table 3*. *Table 3* also includes the group name and the absolute or percentage group size.

Table 3. Performance cluster after the average exam grade EM and HM after semester 1

Cluster	grade	Group size (percentage)
A	> = 1; < 2	14 (7,14)
B	> = 2; < 3	35 (17,86)
C	> = 3; < 4	62 (31,63)
D	> = 4	85 (43,37)
total		196 (100,0)

Grades > 4 were also taken into account. This may be confusing from the examination point of view, because examinations that are graded with grades > 4 are usually considered as "failed". Since, however, an average grade of the written exam was used for this examination, cases arise in which, for example, one written exam was passed and one failed. The variable "average exam grade" therefore does not represent a grade under examination, but rather a professional level of achievement that the students achieved at the end of the first semester.

It becomes clear that a large part (about 43%) of the examined sample can be found in the performance cluster D. Thus, a part of these students did not pass at least one of the two exams (all grades are from initial tests, results of possible final examinations are not taken into account).

5.2 ACHIEVED SOLUTION RATES OF THE PERFORMANCE CLUSTERS

In the next step, the examination of the performance clusters focuses on the achievements in the test for mathematical knowledge at the beginning of the studies (RF_T1). *Table 4* shows the solution rates of the specific clusters and the respective standard deviations.

Table 4. Solution rates of the performance cluster in test RF_T1

Cluster	Solution rate	Standard deviation
A	.78	.23
B	.67	.22
C	.54	.27
D	.45	.26

It is clear that the performance in the test for mathematical knowledge (RF_T1) differ and decrease with higher letter designation of the clusters, and thus with a higher average exam score. Here, the significant correlation that has been shown in the regression model in *Table 1* between RF_T1 and the average exam score becomes clear.

However, this relationship between the mathematical knowledge at the start of the course and the exam performance is not only shown in specific but in all mathematical content areas of the test instrument. This becomes clear in the following diagram (*Fig. 1*). The content areas are color-coded as follows: calculation, trigonometry, vectors and matrices, integrating, terms and equations and differentiation. Thus, research

question 1 can be answered: the solution rates of the test tasks are not directly related to the mathematical content areas.

Fig. 1. Solution rates in RF_T1 of the performance clusters (read: LQ_A_T1: Solution rate in performance cluster A at the start of the study (measurement time T1))

With reference to research question 2, it is evident that the deficits in mathematical knowledge at the beginning of studies and at the end of the first semester are not the same for all students. Nevertheless, about 43%, and thus the majority of students in the cohort (see Table 3 - PC_D), have very large mathematical deficits.

Table 5 shows the achieved solution rates of the performance clusters for T2.

Table 5. Solution rates of the performance cluster in test RF_T2

Cluster	Solution rate	Standard deviation
A	.81	.19
B	.70	.22
C	.52	.25
D	.39	.27

All content areas of the test instrument RF are represented in the group of items with large solution rates differences. For example, within the group of 11 items with large differences in solution rates - both T1 and T2, one item refers to the "calculation" content area, five items to the "terms and equations" area, two items to the "vectors and matrices" area, one item for the differentiate area, one item for the integrate area, and two items for the trigonometry area.

The comparison of the two measurement points with the focus on the solution rates shows after the first semester that the students of the performance clusters A and B tend to show higher, the students of the performance clusters C and D tend to show lower test performances.

6 SUMMARY

In this empirical research project, it could be shown that subject-specific variables at the beginning of studies (eg. mathematical knowledge and the subject-specific modeling ability) explain the achievements in examinations for EM and HM after the

first semester (variable study success). These variables explain additional variance to the variable grade of university entrance qualification (see also [5]).

The strong connection between the mathematical knowledge at the start of the study and the exam performance at the end of the first semester becomes more evident when the sample is divided into performance clusters. Depending on these performance clusters, item-specific, sometimes very large performance differences can be seen. Thus, there is no influence of the mathematical content areas on the solution rates difference. Rather, all content areas are represented in the items with low as well as in the items with high solution rates differences. Thus, the difficulty of mathematical knowledge tasks in this study does not seem to depend on the content but rather on task-related complexity facets not specified in this study.

The primary aim of this paper was to describe the differences between undergraduate students in mathematical engineering at the beginning and end of the first semester on the content level. The use of the test items for the mathematical knowledge of T2 allows a consideration of the performance development of the subjects. There are performance differences between the performance clusters both at the beginning of the study and at the end of the first semester. T2 shows very similar differences in solution rates between the performance clusters. In particular, between the performance clusters A and D is rather an increase in the solution rates differences. That means that the subjects of the performance cluster D are not able to noticeably reduce the performance differences within the first semester, they tend to get bigger. At the same time, the differences at the item level of T1 are almost unchanged.

This is a remarkable finding, since the test contents for mathematical knowledge in the opinion of teachers of the EM and HM have great significance for the knowledge and understanding development in both subjects in the first semester (see [10, 11]). According to the results of this study, it can be assumed that a large number of students in the first semester of their studies fail to work through their basic subject-specific deficits. Also from the perspective of the performance clusters oriented grades of the written exam, these subject-specific deficits represent a risk for passing the exams in EM and HM after the first semester.

This raises the question to why, in particular, the students of the PC_D do not succeed in working up their deficits in the area of mathematical knowledge within the first semester. In particular, it should be asked whether the teaching and learning opportunities available at the universities are suitable for supporting students in the development of basic knowledge and skills.

From our perspective, it is appropriate to examine which specific support for students of civil engineering is needed. The findings of this study show that the independent development of basic mathematics skills is unlikely to be expected of students in the first semester. Here it is to be considered whether further institutional teaching and learning offers are meaningful and affordable. In particular, with regard to the participants' motivation to participate in support programs, measures to increase the student's liabilities are to be examined.

This study provides a well-founded, but limited view of the students' situation in the introductory phase in civil engineering and the links to academic success. Thus, the marks of the first test were used as characteristics of the study success. However, many students succeed in the second attempt, which will be taken into account in the further analysis in this study.

With regard to the individual items, there is no correlation to the mathematical content in the test. It has to be clarified, if missing previous knowledge are the only characteristics of the task difficulty or if there are further difficulties determining characteristics with these test tasks. For example, process analyzes with the cohort of comparable subjects can be carried out. In addition, the items will be examined for already proven difficulty-determining traits.

With regard to the development of mathematical knowledge within the first semester, it has to be clarified why this is largely absent, especially among students in PC_D. Which strategies use students in the first semester in order to cope with the demands of everyday life (exercises, etc.) and what significant role plays the basic mathematical knowledge demanded in the test?

Finally, for the development and orientation of specialist support measures in the introductory phase, it must be clarified which support requirements first-year-students actually have. It can be assumed that students who have mathematical knowledge but have not sufficiently solidified it have different support needs than students whose curriculum at school did not include certain content.

The development of mathematical knowledge within the first semester is a "black box" in this study. For example, there is no information available about which teaching and learning offers or which learning strategies the students have used. However, this information is particularly important for the development of individual support measures.

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